

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART X. SOME N¹- AND N⁴-ALKYLENE BIS-SULPHANILAMIDES*

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Sulphanilamide and potassium salt of acetylsulphanilamide have been condensed with various alkylene dibromides to give N⁴- and N¹-alkylene bis-sulphanilamides, respectively.

Trefouel *et al.* (*Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1937, 58, 30) found N¹-alkyl and N¹-dialkyl derivatives of sulphanilamide to be active against experimental streptococcal infection. Buttle, Grey and Stephenson (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 724) have, however, reported that N¹-diethylsulphanilamide is more toxic than sulphanilamide. Crossley *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2222) have reported that some alkyl disulphanilamides are better than sulphanilamide against β -hemolytic streptococcal infection in mice. Man and Watson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 606) also prepared some simple poly-sulphanilamides in order to test their activity against malarial infection.

With a view to preparing sulpha-derivatives having sulphanilamide molecule linked at either end of an alkylene chain of varying length at N⁴ and N¹ position, the action of various alkylene dibromides on sulphanilamide and potassium salt of N⁴-acetylaminobenzenesulphonamide has been studied. While the alkylene chain may reduce the solubility of the drug in common organic solvents, it may possibly render the molecule more fat-soluble. The two sulphanilamide residues in this case are expected to exert their potency as a general bacteriostatic agent.

Crossley *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 532) prepared 1:2-bis-sulphanilamidoethane (N¹) by reacting *p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride with ethylenediamine, and Northey and Hulquist (U. S. patent No. 2258162) reported it to be therapeutically active. According to Walker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 686), if any alkyl halide reacts with sulphanilamide, then N⁴-amino group is preferentially alkylated; however, with N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide, alkylation takes place entirely at N¹-position. Preparation of potassium salt of N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide makes it still more suitable for reaction.

Various alkylene dibromides chosen for the present work are methylene, ethylene, tri-, tetra- and penta-methylene dibromides.

When the potassium salt of N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide is reacted with the different alkylene dihalides and the resulting acetyl derivatives hydrolysed, alkylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamides of type (A) (II), (IV), (V), (VI), and (VII) result. While the acetyl derivatives (I) and (III) corresponding to (II) and (IV) respectively have been obtained in a pure state, those corresponding to (V), (VI) and (VII) could not be isolated in a pure state.

By the action of various alkylene dibromides on sulphanilamide, the alkylene-bis-N⁴-sulphanilamides (VIII), (IX), (X), (XI) and (XII) of type (B) are obtained.

TYPE A

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|--------------------------------|-------|--------------|-------|
| (I) R = -COCH ₃ ; | n = 1 | (V) R = H; | n = 3 |
| (II) R = H; | n = 1 | (VI) R = H, | n = 4 |
| (III) R = -COCH ₃ ; | n = 2 | (VII) R = H; | n = 5 |
| (IV) R = H; | n = 2 | | |

TYPE B

- (VIII) n = 1; (IX) n = 2; (X) n = 3; (XI) n = 4; (XII) n = 5.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide) (I).—Dry powdered potassium salt of acetylsulphanilamide (10 g.) and methylene dibromide (10 c.c.) were taken in a soda water bottle and heated under pressure in an oil-bath at 120-130° for 6 hours. The excess of methylene dibromide was steam-distilled and the product obtained, was filtered hot after boiling with water (40 c.c.). It was not possible to crystallise it from common organic solvents and hence it was purified by precipitation with acid from its dilute alkali solution, filtered, washed well with water and alcohol and dried as white amorphous powder, m. p. 210°, yield 7.8 g. (Found: N, 13.07; S, 14.5. C₁₁H₂₀O₄N₄S₂ requires N, 12.72; S, 14.47 per cent).

Methylene-bis-N¹-(sulphanilamide) (II).—Methylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide) (4 g.) was refluxed for 1½ hours with hydrochloric acid (15%, 30 c.c.). The solution was filtered and the product obtained on neutralisation with alkali. It was collected by filtration, washed with water and alcohol and dried as a light coloured, amorphous powder, m.p. 296° (decomp.), yield 2.3 g. (Found: N, 15.38; S, 17.56. C₁₂H₁₆O₄N₄S₂ requires N, 15.73; S, 17.97 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide) (III).—Potassium salt of acetylsulphanilamide (10 g.) and ethylene dibromide (12 c.c.) were heated together under reflux in an oil-bath at 150-155° for 6 hours. The excess of ethylene dibromide was then steam-distilled and the residual solid was ground with hot water (20 c.c.) and filtered. The hot water-insoluble product was washed well with further quantities of hot water and the product dried in an air-oven. The product was found insoluble in the usual organic solvents. It was precipitated from its dilute alkali solution by acid, filtered, washed well with water and alcohol, and finally dried as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 275°, yield 8.1 g. (Found: N, 12.37; S, 14.2. C₁₂H₂₂O₄N₄S₂ requires N, 12.33; S, 14.03 per cent).

Ethylene bis-N¹-(sulphanilamide) (IV).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide) (2.5 g.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (15%, 30 c.c.) for 2 hours. The solution

was filtered and neutralised with dilute alkali. The hydrolysed product came up as a white precipitate which was collected by filtration, washed well with water and alcohol, and dried. The product was insoluble in common organic solvents and hence could not be crystallised. The compound was purified by precipitation from its dilute alkali solution with acid after treating with charcoal (norit). The product was finally filtered, washed and dried as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 228°, yield, 1.5 g. (Found : N, 15.3 ; S, 17.4. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 15.14 ; S, 17.29 per cent).

Trimethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (V).—Potassium salt of acetylsulphanilamide (10 g.) and trimethylene dibromide (10 c.c.) were refluxed for 6 hours at 150-160° in an oil-bath. When the excess trimethylene dibromide was removed by steam-distillation, a sticky product resulted. As this crude product could not be purified, it was directly hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid (15%, 40 c.c.) by refluxing for 2 hours. The pasty product, obtained on neutralising the filtrate with dilute alkali, was purified by twice precipitation from its dilute alkali solution by acid after having treated with norit. It was obtained as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 170°, yield 3 g. (Found : N, 14.8 ; S, 16.31. $C_{15}H_{20}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 14.55 ; S, 16.66 per cent).

Tetramethylene-bis-N¹-(sulphanilamide) (VI).—Potassium salt of acetylsulphanilamide (1.5 g.) and tetramethylene dibromide (3 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours at 150-160°. The starting materials were removed and the acetyl product directly hydrolysed as in (V). The crude product was purified by precipitation with acid from its dilute alkali solution after treating with norit and finally extracted with ether. The ether extract on evaporation gave a dry amorphous powder, m.p. 150°, yield 0.5 g. (Found : N, 13.7 ; S, 15.71. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 14.07 ; S 16.08 per cent).

Pentamethylene-bis-N¹-(sulphanilamide) (VII).—Potassium salt of acetylsulphanilamide (2 g.) and pentamethylene dibromide (4 c.c.) were reacted together and the product isolated and purified as in (VI) as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 142°, yield 0.9 g. (Found ; N, 13.2 ; S, 15.1. $C_{17}H_{24}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 13.59 ; S, 15.53 per cent).

Methylene-bis-N⁴-sulphanilamide (VIII).—Sulphanilamide (6 g.) and methylene dibromide (10 c.c.) were reacted together under pressure as described in (I). The excess of methylene dibromide was steam-distilled and unreacted sulphanilamide removed by grinding the product with dilute hydrochloric acid. The product could not be crystallised from the usual organic solvents. The product was purified by precipitation from its alkali solution with acid after treating with norit as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 196°, yield 2.6 g. (Found : N, 15.4 ; S, 17.4. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 15.73 ; S, 17.97 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N⁴-sulphanilamide (IX).—Sulphanilamide (10 g.) and ethylene dibromide (10 c.c.) were heated under reflux for 6 hours at 140-150° in an oil-bath. The starting materials were removed as described in (VIII). The acid-insoluble portion was insoluble in organic solvents and was crystallised twice from water as white silky needles, m.p. 204°, yield 3.5 g. (Found : N, 15.65 ; S, 16.85. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 15.15 ; S, 17.29 per cent).

Trimethylene-bis-N⁴-sulphanilamide (X).—Sulphanilamide (5 g.) and trimethylene dibromide (5 c.c.) were refluxed together for 5 hours at 160-170°. The excess halide was steam-distilled and the residual brown paste directly dissolved in dilute alkali.

The alkali solution was treated with charcoal (norit), filtered and acidified by excess dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid-insoluble product was removed and purified by precipitation as described in (V) as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 180°, yield 1.1 g. (Found : N, 14.13 ; S, 16.10. $C_{15}H_{20}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 14.55 ; S, 16.66 per cent).

Tetramethylene-bis-N⁴-sulphanilamide (XI).—Sulphanilamide (2 g.) and tetramethylene dibromide (4 c.c.) were reacted together and the product obtained as in (X) as a white powder, m.p. 138°, yield 1.1 g. (Found : N, 13.97 ; S, 15.5. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 14.07 ; S, 16.08 per cent).

Pentamethylene-bis-N⁴-sulphanilamide (XII).—Sulphanilamide (2 g.) and pentamethylene dibromide (3 c.c.) were reacted together and the product obtained as in (X) as a white powder, m.p. 155°, yield 1.2 g. (Found ; N, 13.5 ; S, 15.5. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 13.59 ; S, 15.53 per cent).

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